

Viscometric and thermodynamic studies of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions in the solutions of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in purely aqueous and aqueous thiourea media at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

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Abstract : Viscosities (η) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of solutions of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes (NaCl, KCl, NH_4Cl , NaNO_3 , KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and BaCl_2 , MgCl_2 , $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) in purely aqueous and aqueous thiourea solutions have been determined at (293.15, 303.15 and 313.15) K. These data have been used to calculate the constants of Jones-Dole and Masson's equations. Activation thermodynamic quantities ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, $\Delta S_2^{0\#}$, $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow have also been obtained. From the values of these parameters conclusions in regard to ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions have been obtained. It has also been found that all the electrolytes behave as structure makers in purely aqueous and aqueous thiourea solutions.

Keywords : Viscosity, electrolyte, aqueous thiourea.

Introduction

Partial molar volumes of electrolytes provide valuable information about ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions^{1,2}. This information is of fundamental importance for understanding the reaction rates and equilibria involving dissolved electrolytes.

The structural interactions of non-ionic solutes with ionic ones in different solvents are important in many fields of chemistry. The studies of such interactions of non-electrolytes with electrolytes in solution are very significant and useful for investigating their physico-chemical behaviour³⁻¹². Robinson *et al.*^{13,14} and Vishnu *et al.*¹⁵⁻²⁰ have studied aqueous and non-aqueous ternary system containing polyhydroxy compounds and electrolytes like alkali halides. Ultrasonic propagation parameters have been used to study interactions in binary²¹⁻²³ and ternary²⁴⁻²⁶ systems in aqueous^{27,28} and mixed aqueous²⁹ and non-aqueous^{30,31} systems.

Survey of literature reveals that although many studies on thermodynamic properties of various electrolytes have been carried out in single component and in mixed solvent systems, little attention has been paid to the behaviour of different electrolytes in binary aqueous solutions of thiourea. With this in view, viscometric and

thermodynamic studies of aqueous solutions of some uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes, viz. NaCl, KCl, NH_4Cl , NaNO_3 , KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 (uni-univalent) and BaCl_2 , MgCl_2 , $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (bi-univalent) in the presence of thiourea have been undertaken in the light of following aspects :

(i) Determination of viscosities of the solutions of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in aqueous medium in the absence and presence of thiourea at different temperatures; and analysis of viscosity data in the light of Jones-Dole equation vis-à-vis ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions; (ii) Determination of apparent molar volume, V_ϕ of the aqueous solutions of the electrolytes as a function of molar concentration in the absence and presence of thiourea and analysis of V_ϕ -concentration data in the light of Masson's equation vis-à-vis ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions; (iii) Determination of free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, per mole of solvent and solute respectively at different temperatures with a view to obtain additional information regarding structure-making/breaking capacities of electrolytes in purely aqueous medium as well as in the presence of thiourea; and (iv) Calculation of entropy of activation ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) and enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) at different tem-

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peratures for the viscous flow of the aqueous solutions of electrolytes in the absence and presence of thiourea.

Results and discussion

Densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of 0.10 mol dm⁻³ thiourea have been determined as the function of molar concentration (C) of these electrolytes at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 \pm 0.01 K. Representative data in respect of NaCl have been presented in Table 1.

The viscosity data of the electrolytes solutions were

analysed by using Jones-Dole equation³²

$$\eta/\eta_0 = \eta_{rel} = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (1)$$

or

$$(\eta_{rel} - 1)/\sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

where η_0 and η are the dynamic viscosities of solvent and solution respectively; η_{rel} is the relative viscosity of the solution.

The values of coefficient A and B have been obtained from the linear plots of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} by the least squares method and values are listed in Table 2. A

Table 1. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of NaCl in water and in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea at different temperatures

[Thiourea]→ (mol dm ⁻³)	0.0			0.10		
[NaCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	V_ϕ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	η (mPa.s)	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	V_ϕ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
			Temp. 293.15 K			
↓						
0.0	0.9982	1.0020	-	1.0003	1.0046	-
0.2	1.0069	1.0326	15.03	1.0021	1.0134	14.40
0.4	1.0142	1.0557	18.39	1.0112	1.0216	13.50
0.6	1.0222	1.0705	18.52	1.0173	1.0317	12.70
0.8	1.0300	1.0912	18.79	1.0353	1.0419	12.20
1.0	1.0379	1.1120	18.81	1.0644	1.0522	11.20
1.2	1.0456	1.1336	19.00	1.0811	1.0636	10.30
1.4	1.0531	1.1574	19.27	1.0828	1.0728	10.60
1.6	1.0609	1.1733	19.30	1.0999	1.0852	8.80
1.8	1.0687	1.1851	19.34	1.1248	1.0962	8.20
2.0	1.0764	1.2022	19.36	1.1461	1.1083	8.50
			Temp. 303.15 K			
0.0	0.9957	0.7977	-	0.8249	1.0024	-
0.2	1.0041	1.0304	16.48	0.9983	1.0097	16.20
0.4	1.0116	1.0519	18.66	1.0041	1.0176	13.80
0.6	1.0193	1.0751	19.14	1.0139	1.0266	13.20
0.8	1.0270	1.0993	19.31	1.0345	1.0363	12.90
1.0	1.0348	1.1197	19.33	1.0451	1.0476	11.40
1.2	1.0427	1.1315	19.35	1.0693	1.0579	11.10
1.4	1.0505	1.1503	19.36	1.0746	1.0679	10.20
1.6	1.0583	1.1758	19.37	1.0913	1.0805	9.60
1.8	1.0661	1.1945	19.39	1.1087	1.0906	9.40
2.0	1.0739	1.2150	19.40	1.1414	1.1009	9.15
			Temp. 313.15 K			
0.0	0.9922	0.6532	-	0.7907	1.0010	-
0.2	1.0001	1.0277	19.03	0.8346	1.0080	16.80
0.4	1.0078	1.0563	19.70	0.8583	1.0172	15.10
0.6	1.0153	1.0744	20.10	0.8746	1.0252	13.90
0.8	1.0228	1.0984	20.40	1.0448	1.0342	13.60

Table-1 (contd.)

1.0	1.0305	1.1210	20.30	1.0653	1.0440	13.10
1.2	1.0375	1.1424	20.90	1.0964	1.0562	12.40
1.4	1.0451	1.1574	20.80	1.1191	1.0676	11.50
1.6	1.0527	1.1771	20.80	1.1313	1.0798	9.90
1.8	1.0592	1.1945	21.40	1.1556	1.0912	9.20
2.0	1.0664	1.5042	21.50	1.1912	1.1032	8.95

Table 2. Values of coefficients *A* and *B* of Jones-Dole equation for the solutions of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea at different temperatures

Electrolytes	<i>A</i> (dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2})		<i>B</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	
	Water	0.10 mol dm ⁻³ thiourea	Water	0.10 mol dm ⁻³ thiourea
	Temp. 293.15 K			
NaCl	0.0369	-0.0401	0.0766	0.0976
KCl	0.0684	-0.0651	0.1478	0.1468
NH ₄ Cl	0.0419	-0.0231	0.1079	0.1121
NaNO ₃	0.0496	-0.0329	0.0949	0.1282
KNO ₃	-0.0377	0.0919	0.1498	0.1624
NH ₄ NO ₃	-0.0440	-0.0519	0.1883	0.2092
BaCl ₂	0.0841	-0.0242	0.1345	0.2237
MgCl ₂	-0.0648	-0.0361	0.1955	0.2644
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	-0.1009	-0.0459	0.1520	0.2663
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	-0.0665	-0.0760	0.2334	0.2861
	Temp. 303.15 K			
NaCl	0.0303	-0.0401	0.0854	0.1002
KCl	0.0673	-0.0840	0.1692	0.1715
NH ₄ Cl	0.0402	-0.0234	0.1151	0.1224
NaNO ₃	0.0277	-0.0431	0.0986	0.1375
KNO ₃	-0.0417	0.0831	0.1540	0.1718
NH ₄ NO ₃	-0.0456	-0.0336	0.1926	0.2194
BaCl ₂	0.0680	-0.0333	0.1454	0.2383
MgCl ₂	-0.0740	-0.0782	0.2103	0.2739
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	-0.1199	-0.0639	0.1653	0.2835
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	-0.0687	-0.0800	0.2471	0.2972
	Temp. 313.15 K			
NaCl	0.0276	-0.0530	0.0900	0.1259
KCl	0.0558	-0.0895	0.1786	0.1874
NH ₄ Cl	0.0045	-0.0259	0.1210	0.1391
NaNO ₃	0.0145	-0.0530	0.1091	0.1412
KNO ₃	-0.0573	0.0116	0.1601	0.1841
NH ₄ NO ₃	-0.0503	-0.0163	0.2064	0.2303
BaCl ₂	0.0619	-0.0432	0.1606	0.2583
MgCl ₂	-0.0920	-0.0925	0.2267	0.2800
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	-0.1316	-0.0754	0.1736	0.2835
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	-0.0701	-0.0887	0.2595	0.3176

perusal of this Table reveals that in purely aqueous solutions of NaCl, KCl, NH₄Cl, NaNO₃ and BaCl₂ the values of *A* are positive which indicate the presence of strong ion-ion interactions in the aqueous solutions of these electrolytes. Further, in these solutions the values of *A* decrease with the rise in temperatures showing thereby that ion-ion interactions are weakened at elevated temperatures. This may be attributed to the increase in solvation of ions at elevated temperatures. On the other hand, the values of *A* are negative in the purely aqueous solutions of KNO₃, NH₄NO₃, MgCl₂, Ba(NO₃)₂ and Mg(NO₃)₂ which indicates the presence of weak ion-ion interactions in these solutions. It is found that in aqueous solutions of thiourea, the values of *A* for NaCl, KCl, NH₄Cl, NaNO₃, KNO₃ and BaCl₂ exhibit a reversal in the sign from which it follows that the ion-ion interactions are weakened in these solutions. For the rest of the electrolytes there is no change in the nature of ion-ion interaction in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea.

A perusal of the values of coefficient *B* shows that these are positive both in purely aqueous solutions as well as in aqueous thiourea solutions at different temperatures thereby suggesting the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions in these solutions. Further, the values of *B* tend to become larger at elevated temperatures which indicates that the strength of ion-solvent interactions is increased with the rise of temperature.

The apparent molar volume (*V*_φ) for the solutions of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in purely aqueous medium as well as in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea has been determined as a function of molar concentration (*C*) at different temperatures, and representative data in respect of NaCl are presented in Table 1.

The *V*_φ - *C* data have been analysed in the light of Masson's equation³³

$$V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (3)$$

where *V*_φ⁰ is the limiting apparent molar volume and is equal to partial molar volume \bar{V}_2^0 at infinite dilution, and *S*_v is the experimental slope. The values of *V*_φ⁰ and *S*_v

have been obtained from these plots by the method of least squares and presented in Table 3. It is seen that the values of S_v are positive for NaCl, KCl, NH_4Cl , NaNO_3 and BaCl_2 in purely aqueous solutions at different temperatures, which suggest the presence of strong ion-ion interactions in these solutions. On the other hand, the values of S_v are negative in the case of purely aqueous

solutions of KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 , $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and MgCl_2 thereby showing the presence of weak ion-ion interactions. In the presence of 0.10 mol dm^{-3} aqueous thiourea solution, the values of S_v for NaCl, KCl, NH_4Cl , NaNO_3 , BaCl_2 , MgCl_2 , $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ are negative thereby indicating the presence of weak ion-ion interactions in these solutions.

Table 3. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_ϕ^0) and experimental slope (S_v) for the solutions of some uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and in 0.10 mol dm^{-3} aqueous thiourea at different temperatures

Electrolytes	V_ϕ^0 ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		S_v ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ dm}^{3/2} \text{ mol}^{-3/2}$)	
	Water	0.10 mol dm^{-3} thiourea	Water	0.10 mol dm^{-3} thiourea
	Temp. 293.15 K			
NaCl	15.29	17.32	3.28	-14.47
KCl	26.93	27.45	4.18	-2.95
NH_4Cl	34.83	35.32	3.59	-4.23
NaNO_3	27.96	28.17	4.53	-2.84
KNO_3	38.24	39.30	-10.17	3.96
NH_4NO_3	46.34	47.99	-12.93	7.01
BaCl_2	22.69	23.68	4.46	-4.50
MgCl_2	14.72	15.93	-0.68	-1.38
$\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	44.03	46.48	-4.31	-4.23
$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	36.80	37.31	-0.17	-9.21
	Temp. 303.15 K			
NaCl	16.81	18.39	2.16	-6.80
KCl	27.45	28.59	-6.87	-2.95
NH_4Cl	35.96	37.11	2.66	-4.28
NaNO_3	28.97	29.93	1.43	-2.86
KNO_3	39.12	40.55	-11.33	3.01
NH_4NO_3	47.55	48.22	-14.77	6.10
BaCl_2	23.37	24.98	2.36	-6.17
MgCl_2	15.90	16.85	-0.72	-2.24
$\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	45.58	47.91	4.82	-4.80
$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	37.97	39.83	-1.53	-9.36
	Temp. 313.15 K			
NaCl	18.39	19.93	2.16	-7.53
KCl	28.75	29.80	-8.75	-4.45
NH_4Cl	36.13	37.90	1.39	-6.19
NaNO_3	29.30	30.56	0.67	-4.92
KNO_3	41.23	42.01	-11.38	2.71
NH_4NO_3	49.95	50.97	-15.61	5.70
BaCl_2	24.95	25.58	2.44	-7.83
MgCl_2	16.57	17.12	-1.44	-2.35
$\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	46.53	48.64	-5.06	-6.22
$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	38.62	40.96	-6.66	-12.70

A perusal of the values of V_ϕ^0 shows that these are positive in purely aqueous solutions as well as in 0.10 mol dm^{-3} aqueous thiourea solutions of all the electrolytes at different temperatures thereby showing the existence of strong ion-solvent interactions in purely aqueous solutions as well as in aqueous thiourea solutions. Further, with the rise in temperature, the values of V_ϕ^0 tend to increase suggesting thereby the increased strength of ion-solvent interactions at elevated temperatures which may be attributed to the increased solvation of ions³⁴. It is also seen that in the presence of 0.10 mol dm^{-3} thiourea solution, the values of V_ϕ^0 for all electrolytes used in the present study are rendered larger as compared to those in purely aqueous solutions thereby showing that the ion-solvent interactions become stronger in the presence of thiourea.

From the foregoing discussion it is seen that identical conclusions in regard to ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions are obtained on the basis of the values of parameters of Jones-Dole and Masson's equations.

The partial molar volumes of transfer at infinite dilution ($\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$) from water to mixed solvent (water + thiourea) at different temperatures have been calculated using the following equation³⁵

$$\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0 = V_\phi^0(\text{mixed solvent}) - V_\phi^0(\text{water}) \quad (4)$$

The values of $\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$ have been presented in Table 4. It is seen that the values of $\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$ are positive for all electrolytes at different temperatures which may be attributed³⁵ to the decrease in electrostriction effect in the presence of thiourea. Thus, the electrostriction effect which brings about the shrinkage in the volume of water, is decreased in (thiourea + water) mixed solvent as compared with that in pure water.

Free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, per mole of solvent and solute respectively have been calculated as below :

The coefficient B of the Jones-Dole equation is related to the free energy of activation by the following

Table 4. Partial molar volumes of transfer at infinite dilution, ($\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$) for the solutions of some uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea at different temperatures

Electrolyte	$(\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0)$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
NaCl	2.04	1.58	1.54
KCl	0.52	1.14	1.05
NH ₄ Cl	0.49	1.15	1.77
NaNO ₃	0.21	0.96	1.27
KNO ₃	1.07	1.43	0.78
NH ₄ NO ₃	1.65	0.67	1.02
BaCl ₂	0.99	1.61	0.63
MgCl ₂	1.22	0.95	0.55
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	2.45	2.33	2.11
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	0.51	1.86	2.34

equation³⁶ :

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} [(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#})/RT] \quad (5)$$

where \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute respectively. $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of pure solvent and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the free energy of the activation per mole of solute. These were calculated using the following equations³⁷ :

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0} [1000B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (7)$$

where R , h and N are gas constant, Plank constant and Avogadro's number respectively; and T is the absolute temperature.

The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ have been presented in Tables 5 and 6 respectively. It is seen that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for all the uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes are larger both in purely aqueous solutions as well as in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea solutions as compared to those of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and that in each case, $(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}) > 0$. This shows³⁶ that all the uni-univalent and

Table 5. Free energy of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ for water and 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea at different temperatures

Solvent system	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Water	9.31	9.05	8.84
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ Thiourea	9.37	9.12	8.91

Table 6. Values of free energy of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea at different temperatures

Solvent system	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Water	NaCl		
	9.99	11.74	12.96
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	KCl		
	21.98	22.60	26.32
Water	NH ₄ Cl		
	21.19	24.90	27.16
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	KNO ₃		
	29.62	33.49	36.38
Water	BaCl ₂		
	16.86	18.55	20.01
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	MgCl ₂		
	26.23	28.13	30.94
Water	NaNO ₃		
	14.18	15.27	17.27
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	KNO ₃		
	27.41	29.19	30.21
Water	NH ₄ NO ₃		
	22.99	24.41	26.30
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	BaCl ₂		
	33.34	35.25	37.77
Water	MgCl ₂		
	29.29	30.97	34.20
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	Ba(NO ₃) ₂		
	40.60	42.71	45.52
Water	Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
	18.82	21.02	24.03
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	Ba(NO ₃) ₂		
	39.32	42.13	45.85
Water	Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
	25.98	29.02	32.32
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	Ba(NO ₃) ₂		
	44.28	45.83	47.66
Water	Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
	24.07	26.89	29.00
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
	47.88	49.71	52.53
Water	Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
	34.09	37.23	40.19
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
	49.27	52.08	56.21

bi-univalent electrolytes used in present study are structure makers in water as well as in (thiourea + water) mixed solvent system.

The entropy and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow have been obtained as below :

The entropy of activation ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) for different uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes has been calculated from the following relation³⁶ :

$$\frac{d(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#})}{dT} = -\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (8)$$

The enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) has been calculated

with the help of the following equation³⁶ :

$$\Delta H_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\#} + T\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (9)$$

The values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ at different temperatures have been presented in Table 7. It is seen that the values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ are negative for all the uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and also in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea solution. This indicates that the transition state is associated with bond making and increase in order³⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the present study were of

analytical reagent grade and were obtained from Merck. Double distilled water (sp. cond. $\sim 1 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used for the preparation of solutions.

Solutions of uni-univalent electrolytes, viz. NaNO₃, KNO₃, NH₄NO₃, NaCl, KCl, NH₄Cl and NH₄NO₃ and bi-univalent electrolytes, viz. BaCl₂, MgCl₂, Ba(NO₃)₂ and Mg(NO₃)₂ of varying concentrations, in the range 0.0 to 2.0 mol dm⁻³, were prepared in water and in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea. All the solutions were kept in tightly sealed measuring flasks to minimize absorption of atmospheric moisture and carbon dioxide. The weighing was done on a Mettler electronic balance with an accuracy of $\pm 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ g.

Table 7. Values of entropy of activation, $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and enthalpy of activation $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ for viscous flow of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea at different temperatures

Solvent system	$T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
				NaCl		
Water	-43.52	-45.01	-46.49	-33.53	-33.27	-33.53
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-38.21	-39.52	-40.82	-20.89	-21.13	-20.89
				KCl		
Water	-87.57	-90.56	-93.54	-66.38	-65.65	-66.38
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-99.17	-102.55	-105.94	-69.55	-69.06	-69.55
				NH ₄ Cl		
Water	-46.17	-47.74	-49.31	-29.30	-29.19	-29.30
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-69.01	-71.36	-73.72	-42.78	-43.24	-42.78
				NaNO ₃		
Water	-45.29	-46.83	-48.38	-31.11	-31.56	-31.11
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-40.98	-42.38	-43.78	-13.57	-13.18	-13.57
				KNO ₃		
Water	-48.55	-50.20	-51.86	-31.71	-32.01	-31.71
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-65.05	-67.26	-69.48	-31.71	-32.01	-31.71
				NH ₄ NO ₃		
Water	-72.00	-74.45	-76.91	-31.53	-31.88	-31.53
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-72.13	-74.59	-77.05	-31.53	-31.88	-31.53
				BaCl ₂		
Water	-76.46	-79.07	-81.67	-57.64	-58.05	-57.64
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-287.35	-297.15	-306.95	-56.36	-56.82	-56.36
				MgCl ₂		
Water	-92.83	-96.00	-99.16	-66.85	-66.97	-66.85
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-49.43	-51.12	-52.80	-5.15	-5.29	-5.15
				Ba(NO ₃) ₂		
Water	-72.26	-74.73	-77.19	-20.35	-20.84	-20.35
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-68.23	-70.56	-72.88	-20.35	-20.84	-20.35
				Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
Water	-89.38	-92.43	-95.48	-55.29	-55.19	-55.29
0.10 mol dm ⁻³ aqueous Thiourea	-294.01	-304.03	-314.06	-52.45	-53.11	-52.45

Densities of the solutions were measured at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K with an Anton Parr digital vibrating tube densimeter. The uncertainty of the density measurements was estimated to be $\pm 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

Viscosities were measured with a calibrated U-type Ostwald's viscometer with sufficiently long efflux time (~200 s) to avoid kinetic energy correction. Temperature was controlled by a thermostatic water bath fluctuating to $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$. The uncertainty of η in the present experiments was $\pm 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mPa.s}$. The relative viscosities of the solutions were calculated from the following equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \eta_{\text{rel}} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \cdot \frac{t}{t_0} \quad (10)$$

where η_0 and η are the dynamic viscosities of solvent and solution respectively; η_{rel} is the relative viscosity of the solution, ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the solution and solvent respectively, t and t_0 are the flow times of the solution and solvent respectively.

Determination of apparent molar volume (V_ϕ):

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ aqueous thiourea were determined as a function of molar concentration (C) of the electrolytes at different temperatures (293.15, 303.15 and 313.15) K using the following equation,

$$V_\phi = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{C\rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho_0} \quad (11)$$

where C is the molarity of the solutions of the electrolytes, ρ is the density of the solution, ρ_0 is the density of solvent and M is the molecular weight of the solute.

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